

The Influence of Interpersonal Interaction on Academic Interest of Undergraduate Top Students: The Mediating Role of Academic Confidence

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Abstract

Academic interest is the core driving force for the growth of top innovative talents. Interpersonal interaction and academic confidence are important factors influencing the formation and development of academic interest among top undergraduate students. To deeply explore the mechanisms among these three factors, this study conducted a questionnaire survey involving 350 top undergraduate students. The findings reveal that interpersonal interaction has a significant positive promoting effect on academic interest, with variations in the impact of different types of interactions. Academic confidence plays a partial mediating role between interpersonal interaction and academic interest. Enhancing the quality of interpersonal interaction and strengthening students' academic confidence are effective pathways for cultivating academic interest. Accordingly, recommendations are proposed: optimize interpersonal interaction to build a diversified support system; enhance academic confidence to solidify the psychological foundation of academic interest; and pay attention to individual differences to implement classified training. These measures aim to boost the academic interest of top undergraduate students and provide sustained momentum for talent cultivation.

Keywords: Interpersonal interaction; academic interest; academic confidence; undergraduate top students

1. Introduction

The cultivation of top innovative talents is crucial for implementing the innovation-driven development strategy and enhancing national comprehensive competitiveness. It holds an irreplaceable strategic position in promoting technological self-reliance and self-improvement and in building world-class talent centers and innovation hubs. Higher education, as a vital nexus of science and technology as the primary productive force, talent as the primary resource, and innovation as the primary driving force, bears the important mission of cultivating talent for the nation and must place greater emphasis on the cultivation of top innovative talents.

Undergraduate education is the foundational stage for the growth and development of top innovative talents. Its quality directly relates to the effectiveness of independent talent cultivation and even influences the structure and competitiveness of the nation's future talent pool. Academic interest plays a fundamental and guiding role in the undergraduate education stage, especially for top students. The stability and deepening of their academic interest are not only related to individual growth but are also closely connected to the national reserve of high-level talents and technological competitiveness. However, in reality, some top students still face fluctuations or even decline in academic interest during their undergraduate years. Data shows that since the establishment of the University of

Science and Technology of China's "Special Class for the Gifted Young" 42 years ago, it has trained over 4,000 students, with only about 20% remaining in academia, while the majority entered fields such as enterprise and finance (Fang et al., 2020). Another survey targeting undergraduates in the "Top Student Program" at 12 leading Chinese universities indicates that the "interest in knowledge pursuit" among top students shows a declining trend from freshman to senior year (Lu, 2023). Therefore, how to effectively sustain and deepen their academic interest has become a pressing practical issue in higher education talent cultivation.

The development of academic interest is deeply rooted in the complex interaction between the individual and the environment. Among these, interpersonal interaction constitutes a key external social support. According to social support theory, instrumental and emotional support from family, friends, and others together form an individual's social support system, which in turn affects the individual's development process (Lu, 2023). For top students, high-quality teacher-student and peer interactions can guide their academic development direction, stimulate cognitive collisions, and provide emotional support. Simultaneously, academic confidence constitutes the internal motivational mechanism for individual development. According to Bandura's self-efficacy theory, an individual's confidence in their ability to complete specific tasks directly influences their task choice, level of effort, and behavioral persistence (Lu, 2023). The academic confidence of top students not only affects their level of learning engagement but also has a significant impact on their academic interest. Gan Shaojie et al. (2023) further found through mediation effect analysis that peer interaction can not only directly affect learning engagement but also indirectly affect academic interest through academic confidence. Thus, it appears that both interpersonal interaction and academic confidence influence academic interest to some extent.

Based on this, this study will utilize empirical data to focus on exploring the internal mechanism through which interpersonal interaction affects the academic interest of undergraduate top students, as well as the mediating role of "academic confidence" there in, aiming to provide theoretical basis and empirical support for the cultivation of top innovative talents.

2. Conceptual Definitions

The theoretical understanding of interpersonal interaction has gradually deepened with social development, and its concept in existing research is often based on social interaction theory. Social interaction refers to the dynamic process of mutual influence and interaction in psychology and behavior among individuals, between individuals and groups, and between groups within a specific social context. Based on this theory, this study defines interpersonal interaction as: psychological and behavioral exchanges between undergraduate students and their peers and teachers within the university environment. Specifically, this study focuses on two types: student-student interaction and student-teacher interaction. Student-student interaction includes both academic and non-academic interactions, while student-teacher interaction includes academic and social interactions. Together, these constitute the main dimensions of interpersonal interaction in this study.

As an academic concept with Chinese characteristics, there is currently no consensus on the definition of academic interest in the academic community. This concept encompasses the two dimensions of "zhi" (aspiration) and "qu" (interest). Drawing on the research of Lu Yi and Shi Jinghuan (2015), this study operationally defines it as: undergraduate students' high identification with their professional field, strong interest in academic research or learning activities, willingness to make long-term commitments and dedicate themselves to academic research in this field, and the aspiration to become scientists and contribute to the advancement of scientific endeavors.

Academic confidence is a specific manifestation of self-efficacy in the academic domain, with a more defined focus, used to characterize students' beliefs in their own academic abilities. Drawing on Wan Rui's (2023) perspective, this study specifically defines it as: undergraduate students' belief and judgment in their ability to comprehensively utilize knowledge, skills, and higher-order thinking to successfully complete learning tasks and achieve academic goals in academic contexts.

The concept of “top students” is multi-dimensional and complex. The U.S. Marland Report first systematically proposed that “gifted” performance can encompass general intellectual ability, specific academic aptitude, creative ability, among other areas, a classification widely recognized in academia (Rutigliano et al., 2021). The Chinese policy context also elevates the cultivation of “top innovative talents” to a national strategic level, as reflected in initiatives like the “Strong Foundation Plan”, which emphasizes selecting students with outstanding comprehensive qualities or exceptional ability in basic disciplines (Ministry of Education of the People’s Republic of China, 2018). Based on academic research and policy orientation, this study defines undergraduate top students as those who demonstrate outstanding performance and high potential in academic interest, learning ability, knowledge base, and innovative potential. However, during the undergraduate stage, these traits are often difficult to observe and quantify directly. Therefore, this study primarily relies on academic performance—a widely used core explicit indicator—to operationally define undergraduate top students as “students ranking in the top 30% in academic performance”.

3. Theoretical Foundation

3.1 Interaction Theory

This study is based on interaction theory, which focuses on interactive behaviors in interpersonal communication. Interaction theory mainly comprises two branches: symbolic interactionism and role interactionism. Symbolic interactionism, represented by George H. Mead, features core concepts such as the “I” and the “me”: the “me” represents society’s expectations of the individual, and the “I” is the individual’s response to these expectations. This theory posits that interpersonal interaction requires the use of commonly understood mediating symbols such as spoken language and written text (Mead, 1999), and emphasizes that individuals continuously adjust self-cognition and behavior through interaction to achieve self-development. Role interactionism focuses on the role behaviors exhibited by individuals during interpersonal interaction based on their role awareness and role expectations, with different role contexts giving rise to differentiated behaviors. An individual’s self-cognition plays a decisive role in their interactive behavior (Zhao, 2023).

As typical forms of interpersonal interaction, student-student and student-teacher interactions utilize common symbols such as communication in group cooperation and expression in class discussions to complete information transmission and reach consensus. Students can continuously adjust their self-cognition through symbolic exchange in interactions, while teachers adjust teaching pace based on symbolic feedback. This process enables undergraduate top students to achieve self-cognitive development through symbolic interaction. From the perspective of role interactionism, the role positioning of “cooperation, mutual assistance, and win-win” in student-student interaction, along with mutual recognition among peers, allows individuals to perceive their value in academic collaboration. The sense of academic satisfaction brought by such role experiences can continuously consolidate the academic interest of undergraduate top students. In student-teacher interaction, teachers encouraging students to raise questions, affirming students’ academic potential, and guiding research directions can both ignite the exploration enthusiasm of top students and help them perceive their own academic capabilities, thereby continuously strengthening academic confidence and solidifying the foundation of academic interest. Thus, high-quality student-student and student-teacher interactions effectively enhance the academic confidence level of undergraduate top students, strengthen their academic confidence in the academic field, and deepen their academic interest.

3.2 Social Cognitive Theory

Social cognitive theory, proposed by psychologist Albert Bandura, includes core concepts such as triadic reciprocal determinism, self-efficacy, and social learning theory.

Among these, triadic reciprocal determinism emphasizes the interaction among three factors—personal cognition, environment, and behavior—in jointly influencing an individual’s learning process (Bandura, 2015). Applying this theory to the group of undergraduate top students reveals that in their academic and research practices, personal cognition, environment, and action are closely interrelated, jointly pointing to the cultivation and development of

academic interest. Specifically, personal cognition, as the internal driving force of academic interest, together with the environment as the external driving force, acts on the practical behavior of academic interest (Xu, 2022). For example, in high-quality interpersonal interactions, mutual encouragement among peers, positive feedback from teachers, and the academic opportunities and professional guidance obtained during interaction can deepen top students' recognition of disciplinary value, enhance their academic confidence, and thereby motivate them to engage in more academic practices. Conversely, students' internal drive and sustained academic behaviors will help them build stable interpersonal interaction circles, react back on the environment, and prompt the environment to further deepen academic interest.

Bandura believed that whether an individual implements a certain behavior and can sustain it depends mainly on their perception and belief in their own relevant abilities. This perception and belief is termed "self-efficacy" (Bandura, 1985). In this study, "academic confidence" tends to point more towards research self-efficacy—that is, students' belief in their own research capabilities. According to existing research, research self-efficacy has a significant impact on academic interest. Specifically, in interpersonal interaction scenarios, direct experiences gained by top students through interaction, vicarious experiences from peers and teachers, verbal persuasion, and resulting emotional arousal and other external reinforcement factors can effectively help them enhance confidence and improve research self-efficacy (Wang et al., 2022), thereby encouraging them to invest more time and energy in the academic field.

Social learning theory explains the influence of environmental factors on academic interest. This theory posits that most people's learning often occurs by observing others' behaviors and performances, thereby acquiring knowledge, skills, strategies, and attitudes, etc. (Mead, 1999) Specifically, in interpersonal interaction scenarios, top students can not only learn effective research methods from each other but also form a solid cognitive foundation by observing their teachers' words and actions. This helps them explore their own academic interests and establish academic aspirations.

4. Literature Review and Research Hypotheses

4.1 Literature Review

4.1.1 Research on the Relationship between Interpersonal Interaction and Academic Interest

As the two main subjects in the teaching process, the interaction between teachers and students is related to the formation of students' academic interest. Lu Yi and Shi Jinghuan (2015) found that academic interest is highly correlated with teacher-student interpersonal interaction factors, particularly the exemplary role of academic leaders being crucial for the formation of academic interest. Yang Yang (2024) further pointed out that a mentor's guidance and care play a key role in the formation of graduate students' academic interest. These studies focus on the positive value of teacher-student interaction, affirming the central role of mentors in academic enlightenment and interest guidance. However, teacher-student interaction may also harbor certain educational risks. Wan Rui and Lu Yi (2024) found that the sense of mentor authority in admiring-type relationships may lead to students' excessive dependence, limiting the formation of their independent academic judgment and internal motivation. This finding provides an important supplement to existing research, suggesting that teacher-student relationships need to seek a balance between "guidance" and "autonomy", offering a dimension for dialectical thinking in subsequent research.

Besides mentors, communication and interaction among students are also very common in the learning process. Zhang Mingkai et al. (2021) found in their research that peer support can enhance students' academic confidence, making them more active and diligent in learning activities, thereby strengthening academic interest. This finding has been further confirmed in international research. Furman et al. (1985), Bria et al. (1993), and Terenzini et al. (1996) indicate that good peer interaction can enhance students' sense of security and belonging, create a positive learning environment, and thereby boost their learning motivation and confidence, subsequently enhancing their academic interest. Thus, both domestic and international research show that peer interaction, by building a supportive learning community, provides necessary emotional and practical support for the cultivation of academic interest, and the related perspective extends from the domestic to the international context, enhancing the universality of the conclusion.

4.1.2 Research on the Relationship between Interpersonal Interaction and Academic Confidence

Existing research mainly explores this from two dimensions: mentor support and peer relationships.

Mentor support can enhance students' academic confidence to a certain extent. This support comes from multiple aspects. Yang Yang (2024) believes that a mentor's financial support and guidance can reduce research obstacles, help graduate students form positive research experiences, and thereby improve their academic confidence. Jia Xuji et al.(2020) also found that when teachers prioritize students' problems and needs, it allows students to perceive more teacher support, thereby implicitly enhancing their academic self-efficacy. Although these two studies focus on different aspects of mentor support, they both reveal the internal logic that mentor support indirectly enhances students' academic confidence by reducing academic pressure and strengthening psychological identification, reflecting the diversity and effectiveness of mentor support.

Peer relationships may also impact academic confidence. Scholars Brendgen (2015) and Rose (2006) pointed out that good peer relationships help enhance students' intrinsic sense of value, strengthen their positive attitude towards life, and thereby improve self-efficacy. This research extends the influence of peer relationships from the academic domain to the psychological value level, enriching the study of the pathways through which interpersonal interaction affects academic confidence.

4.1.3 Research on the Relationship between Academic Confidence and Academic Interest

Academic confidence plays a key role in the formation and development of academic interest. Lu Yi and Shi Jinghuan's (2015) empirical study on undergraduate students majoring in life sciences at Tsinghua University confirmed this point. Liu Junnan et al. (2024) made similar findings through interviews—self-efficacy is one of the core elements influencing the academic aspirations of “top students”. Xu Guoxing (2020) further pointed out in data analysis that academic interest is closely related to the degree of active learning participation, indicating that intrinsic learning motivation is more important for the development of academic interest. Yang Yang (2024) therefore speculated that higher academic self-efficacy would keep master's students optimistic when applying for doctoral programs, thereby enhancing academic interest. This is consistent with the findings of foreign scholars such as Usher et al. (2019)—students with high learning efficacy invest more persistently in learning activities, thereby enhancing their academic interest. These studies, from different research paradigms, subjects, and perspectives, collectively reveal the important influence of academic confidence as an internal driving factor on academic interest, laying the foundation for subsequent research.

4.1.4 Literature Review Summary

From existing research, scholars have fully demonstrated the core position of academic interest in the cultivation of top innovative talents and have explored related influencing factors from perspectives such as teacher-student relationships, research participation, and research self-efficacy. However, existing studies often focus on single variables or pairwise relationships, rarely incorporating interpersonal interaction, academic confidence, and academic interest into a unified theoretical framework for systematic investigation. Particularly, attention to “academic confidence” is relatively insufficient, often replaced by concepts like “self-efficacy”, lacking in-depth exploration of its internal mechanism.

Secondly, existing research objects primarily focus on graduate student and doctoral student groups, with relatively little attention paid to undergraduate top students. The undergraduate stage is a critical period for the germination and initial development of students' academic interest. In-depth exploration of this stage is beneficial for constructing a complete talent cultivation system.

In view of this, this study focuses on undergraduate top students, attempting to examine the influence of interpersonal interaction and academic confidence on undergraduates' academic interest from this perspective, reveal the mediating mechanism of academic confidence, and then propose strategies for enhancing the academic interest of undergraduate top students. This aims to provide a theoretical basis for universities to optimize talent cultivation models and stimulate students' research potential, helping the nation cultivate more top innovative talents and promote

technological development and national strength building.

4.2 Research Hypotheses

Based on the preceding literature review, we propose the following hypotheses:

4.2.1 Hypothesis regarding interpersonal interaction and academic confidence of undergraduate top students

Based on self-efficacy theory and existing research, interpersonal interaction experiences have a significant impact on an individual's research self-efficacy (Yang, 2024). Good peer relationships and teacher-student relationships can help top students enhance their intrinsic sense of value and research experience, thereby consolidating and improving academic confidence. Accordingly, this study proposes the following hypothesis:

H1: Interpersonal interaction has a positive influence on the academic confidence of undergraduate top students.

4.2.2 Hypothesis regarding interpersonal interaction and academic interest of undergraduate top students

Existing research indicates that student-student and student-teacher interactions have significant impacts on students' learning engagement, learning interest, and the establishment of aspirations (Lu et al., 2015). Among these, the mentor's own qualities and guidance behaviors are potential forces driving the development of undergraduates' academic interest, while interaction and connection among peers are important motivators for promoting the development of undergraduates' academic interest (Wang, 2023). Accordingly, this study proposes the following hypothesis:

H2: Interpersonal interaction has a positive influence on the academic interest of undergraduate top students.

4.2.3 Hypothesis regarding academic confidence and academic interest of undergraduate top students

Existing research shows that self-efficacy has a significant positive influence on academic interest. Regarding research self-efficacy, research indicates that graduate students' sense of identification and gain from academic research are important factors influencing their academic interest (Kuang et al., 2020). Moreover, students with stronger academic self-efficacy tend to have higher identification and loyalty towards research, leading them to more actively engage in research activities and establish academic ideals. Based on this, and considering the cultivation characteristics of undergraduate top students, this study proposes the following hypothesis:

H3: The academic confidence of undergraduate top students has a positive influence on their academic interest.

4.2.4 Hypothesis regarding the mediating role of academic confidence

Existing research shows that aspects related to academic confidence, such as knowledge reserve and space to utilize strengths, are positively correlated with the academic interest of undergraduate top students (Lu, 2015). Simultaneously, students' own sense of efficacy gradually transforms from “academic confidence” to “research confidence”, and this “research confidence” is an important driving force for them to “feel confident in choosing to continue engaging in research work”. Accordingly, this study proposes the following hypothesis:

H4: Academic confidence plays a mediating role in the influence of interpersonal interaction on the academic interest of undergraduate top students.

In summary, based on hypotheses H1-H4, this study establishes the model as shown in Figure 1:

Figure 1 Research Hypothesis Model

5. Research Methods

5.1 Research Subjects

This study distributed questionnaires online to undergraduate top students. A total of 411 questionnaires were issued, with 350 valid questionnaires screened, resulting in an effective response rate of 85.16%. Among the participants: 121 were male, 229 were female; 36 were freshmen, 75 were sophomores, 122 were juniors, 117 were seniors; 188 were from humanities and social sciences, 136 from science and engineering, 26 from arts and physical education; 91 were from national “Double First-Class” universities, 47 from provincial/municipal “Double First-Class” universities, 125 from provincial key universities, 87 from other undergraduate institutions; 90 currently resided in rural areas, 260 in cities; the highest parental education level was junior high school or below for 110, high school or technical secondary school for 161, and university or above for 79; family monthly income was below 3500 yuan for 27, 3500-7000 yuan for 104, 7000-10000 yuan for 101, and above 10000 yuan for 118.

5.2 Research Instruments

The scales used in this study all employed a 5-point Likert scale, with points 1 to 5 representing increasing levels of agreement (1 = strongly disagree, 2 = somewhat disagree, 3 = neutral, 4 = somewhat agree, 5 = strongly agree). There were no reverse-scored items.

5.2.1 Interpersonal Interaction Scale for Undergraduate Top Students

The Interpersonal Interaction Scale for Undergraduate Top Students was revised based on Sun Mingzhu’s College Student Peer Interaction Survey Questionnaire. It divides interpersonal interaction for undergraduate top students into four dimensions: student-student academic interaction, student-student non-academic interaction, student-teacher academic interaction, and student-teacher social interaction. Among these, the student-student academic interaction dimension consists of 7 items, including statements like “I often engage in group cooperative learning with classmates”. The student-student non-academic interaction dimension has 5 items, including “When communicating daily with classmates, their enthusiasm for academic exploration often inspires me”. The student-teacher academic interaction dimension has 6 items, including “I often actively ask questions or participate in discussions in class”. The student-teacher social interaction dimension has 4 items, including “I often discuss my career plans with teachers”. After reliability and validity analysis, the Cronbach’s α coefficient for this scale was 0.94, indicating good reliability.

5.2.2 Academic Confidence Scale for Undergraduate Top Students

This scale was adapted from the Academic Self-Efficacy Scale compiled by Liang Yusong et al. The entire scale consists of 8 items, including statements like “Regarding learning or research, my knowledge reserve in various subjects is sufficient, solid, and without gaps”. The Cronbach’s α coefficient for this scale was 0.88, indicating good reliability.

5.2.3 Academic Interest Scale for Undergraduate Top Students

The Academic Interest Scale for Undergraduate Top Students was revised based on the Academic Interest Scale compiled by Liu Bohan et al. This scale breaks down academic interest into four dimensions: academic loyalty, academic identification, academic effort, and academic ideal. Each dimension has 4 items. Academic loyalty includes items like “I am passionate about academia”. Academic identification includes items like “I believe academic activities are about seeking truth.” Academic effort includes items like “I have a clear research and study plan for the four undergraduate years”. Academic ideal includes items like “I intend to pursue a master’s degree.” The Cronbach’s α coefficient for this scale was 0.93, indicating good reliability.

5.3 Data Processing and Analysis

The questionnaire data were analyzed using SPSS 26.0 for descriptive analysis, difference analysis, correlation analysis, regression analysis, and mediation effect testing using Model 4 in the PROCESS macro program.

6. Research Results

6.1 Descriptive Analysis

As shown in Table 1, regarding interpersonal interaction, the overall mean for interpersonal interaction was 3.66. The mean scores for each dimension, from high to low, were: student-student non-academic interaction, student-student academic interaction, student-teacher academic interaction, and student-teacher social interaction, with scores of 3.98, 3.71, 3.62, and 3.22, respectively. Regarding academic interest, the overall mean for the scale was 3.75, indicating room for overall improvement. The dimensions of academic interest, from high to low, were: academic identification, academic ideal, academic effort, and academic loyalty, with mean scores of 4.04, 3.75, 3.66, and 3.57, respectively. Regarding academic confidence, the overall mean was 3.75, at a medium level overall, with potential for further improvement.

Table 1 Descriptive Analysis of Each Dimension

Variable	N	Min	Max	Min	SD
Interpersonal Interaction	350	1	5	3.66	0.69
Academic Confidence	350	1	5	3.75	0.69
Academic Interest	350	1	5	3.75	0.69

6.2 Difference Analysis

As can be seen from Table 2: Regarding interpersonal interaction, except for family monthly income, all other demographic variables showed significant differences. Specifically, scores were significantly higher for male students, students from urban areas, sophomores, and students majoring in science and engineering. Regarding school type, scores for students from national “Double First-Class” universities were significantly higher than those from provincial/municipal “Double First-Class” universities, provincial key universities, and other undergraduate institutions. Scores for students whose parents’ education level was high school or university were also significantly higher than those for students whose parents' education level was junior high school or below.

Regarding academic interest and academic confidence, significant differences existed across all demographic variables. Overall, scores were relatively higher for male students, students from urban areas, and students majoring in science and engineering. In terms of grade differences, sophomores performed particularly well in academic interest, while both sophomore and senior students’ academic confidence was significantly higher than that of juniors. Regarding school type, scores for students from national “Double First-Class” universities were significantly better than those from other types of institutions. Higher parental education level was associated with stronger academic interest and academic confidence. Furthermore, family monthly income also showed a significant impact, with scores for groups with monthly income above 3500 yuan being significantly higher than for the group with monthly income below 3500 yuan.

Table 2 Differences in Interpersonal Interaction, Academic Interest, and Academic Confidence among Undergraduate Top Students

	Variable	N	Interpersonal Interaction (M±SD)	Academic Interest (M±SD)	Academic Confidence (M±SD)
Gender	Male	121	3.86±0.63	3.96±0.65	3.97±0.64
	Female	229	3.55±0.70	3.64±0.68	3.64±0.69
	T-value	--	3.81***	1.30***	1.02***
Grade	Freshman	36	3.57±0.67	3.63±0.77	3.69±0.78
	Sophomore	75	3.89±0.51	3.95±0.57	3.92±0.63
	Junior	122	3.51±0.75	3.66±0.71	3.60±0.72

	Variable	N	Interpersonal Interaction (M±SD)	Academic Interest (M±SD)	Academic Confidence (M±SD)
Major Type	Senior	117	3.69±0.70	3.76±0.68	3.83±0.63
	F-value	--	5.03**	3.34*	4.05**
	Humanities	188	3.58±0.70	3.62±0.71	3.65±0.69
	Sciences and Engineering	136	3.79±0.67	3.96±0.61	3.91±0.67
	Arts and Sports	26	3.53±0.67	3.65±0.60	3.68±0.66
Current Residence	F-value	--	4.14*	10.26***	5.83**
	Rural	90	3.50±0.69	3.61±0.71	3.59±0.70
	Urban	260	3.71±0.68	3.80±0.67	3.81±0.68
	T-value	--	0.31**	1.88*	0.28**
	National "Double First-Class"	91	3.86±0.62	3.95±0.66	3.95±0.62
School Type	Provincial/Municipal "Double First-Class"	47	3.88±0.58	3.91±0.57	3.88±0.58
	Provincial Key University	125	3.54±0.71	3.70±0.68	3.69±0.68
	Other Undergraduate Institution	87	3.51±0.72	3.55±0.73	3.58±0.78
	F-value	--	7.05***	6.42***	5.54**
	Junior High School or Below	110	3.48±0.72	3.55±0.67	3.56±0.68
Parental Education	High School or Technical Secondary School	161	3.69±0.65	3.80±0.64	3.82±0.67
	University or Above	79	3.83±0.69	3.93±0.73	3.90±0.69
	F-value	--	6.43**	8.56***	7.26**
	Below 3500 yuan	27	3.41±0.73	3.41±0.82	3.40±0.79
	3500-7000 yuan	104	3.61±0.69	3.71±0.62	3.69±0.68
Family Income	7000-10000 yuan	101	3.73±0.68	3.79±0.67	3.83±0.63
	Above 10000 yuan	118	3.70±0.69	3.84±0.70	3.83±0.72
	F-value	--	1.79	3.11*	3.48*

Note: *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$ (two-tailed test)

6.3 Analysis of the Effects of Interpersonal Interaction, Academic Confidence, and Academic Interest

6.3.1 Common Method Bias Test

Since this study collected data through questionnaires, there might be common method bias. Therefore, this study employed single-factor confirmatory factor analysis to test for common method bias across all scale items involved in hypothesis testing. The results showed poor model fit: $\chi^2/df = 3.671 > 3$, CFI = 0.716 < 0.9, GFI = 0.607 < 0.9, AGFI = 0.572 < 0.9, NFI = 0.648 < 0.9, RMSEA = 0.087 > 0.08. Thus, there was no serious common method bias issue.

6.3.2 Correlation Analysis of Interpersonal Interaction, Academic Confidence, and Academic Interest

In this analysis, Pearson correlation analysis was used to exploratively analyze the correlation relationships among the variables. As can be seen from the Pearson correlation analysis results among the dimensions in Table 3, there were significant correlations among all variables in this analysis. From the correlation coefficient results, the correlation coefficient R among the variables was all greater than 0, indicating that in this analysis, interpersonal interaction, academic confidence, and academic interest all had significant positive correlation relationships.

Table 3 Results of Pearson Correlation Analysis Among Dimensions

Dimension	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
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1.Student-Student Academic Interaction	1								
2.Student-Student Non-Academic Interaction	0.66**	1							
3.Student-Teacher Academic Interaction	0.74**	0.57**	1						
4.Student-Teacher Social Interaction	0.67**	0.50**	0.77**	1					
5.Academic Loyalty	0.59**	0.59**	0.66**	0.58**	1				
6.Academic Identification	0.41**	0.57**	0.48**	0.30**	0.61**	1			
7.Academic Effort	0.69**	0.68**	0.73**	0.64**	0.72**	0.58**	1		
8.Academic Ideal	0.47**	0.52**	0.60**	0.49**	0.64**	0.49**	0.63**	1	
9.Academic Confidence	0.60**	0.62**	0.64**	0.54**	0.68**	0.58**	0.72**	0.67**	1

Note: *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$ (two-tailed test)

6.3.3 Regression Analysis of the Impact of Interpersonal Interaction on Academic Interest

To examine the impact of various dimensions of interpersonal interaction on academic interest, multiple linear regression analysis was conducted. Multicollinearity diagnosis showed that all VIF values were below the critical value of 10, indicating no multicollinearity issues. The results are shown in Table 4.

Different types of interpersonal interaction showed differentiated impacts on the various dimensions of academic interest. Regarding student-student interaction, student-student academic interaction only had a significant positive impact on academic effort ($\beta = 0.15, p < 0.01$). Student-student non-academic interaction not only significantly positively predicted the overall situation of academic interest ($\beta = 0.38, p < 0.001$) but also positively influenced all aspects of academic interest. Based on the standardized coefficients, student-student non-academic interaction had the greatest impact on academic identification ($\beta = 0.49, p < 0.001$), followed by academic effort ($\beta = 0.32, p < 0.001$), academic ideal ($\beta = 0.27, p < 0.001$), and finally academic loyalty ($\beta = 0.26, p < 0.001$).

Regarding student-teacher interaction, student-teacher academic interaction demonstrated a foundational role, having a significant positive predictive effect on all dimensions of academic interest, indicating that formal interactions between teachers and students centered on academic issues are a key path for cultivating students' academic interest. The impact of student-teacher social interaction was relatively limited, only having a weak positive effect on academic loyalty ($\beta = 0.13, p < 0.05$), academic identification ($\beta = 0.28, p < 0.001$), and academic effort ($\beta = 0.13, p < 0.05$), with no significant impact on academic ideal or overall academic interest.

Table 4 Regression Analysis of the Impact of Interpersonal Interaction on Academic Interest

Independent Variables	Model 1: Academic Loyalty	Model 2: Academic Identification	Model 3: Academic Effort	Model 4: Academic Ideal	Model 5: Academic Interest
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	β	t								
Student-Student Academic Interaction	0.06	0.97	-0.10	-1.38	0.15	2.75**	-0.08	-1.13	0.01	0.30
Student-Student Non-Academic Interaction	0.26	4.92***	0.49	8.63***	0.32	7.30***	0.27	4.95***	0.38	8.61***
Student-Teacher Academic Interaction	0.34	4.92***	0.42	5.62***	0.30	5.32***	0.41	5.67**	0.44	7.74***
Student-Teacher Academic Interaction	0.13	2.09*	0.28	5.55***	0.13	2.60*	0.07	1.08	0.06	1.14
F	19.98***		37.37***		36.43***		23.30***		36.03***	
R ²	0.54		0.40		0.68		0.45		0.68	

Note: *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$ (two-tailed test)

6.3.4 Mediation Effect Test of Academic Confidence

To further verify the relationship between interpersonal interaction, academic confidence, and the academic interest of undergraduate top students, and to test the mediating effect of academic confidence between interpersonal interaction and academic interest, this study used Model 4 in the PROCESS macro program for mediation testing. The results are shown in Table 5, and Figure 2 shows the path diagram of the mediation effect model. As can be seen from Table 5, in Model 1, interpersonal interaction significantly positively predicted academic interest ($\beta = 0.75, p < 0.001$), supporting Hypothesis H2. In Model 2, interpersonal interaction significantly positively predicted academic confidence ($\beta = 0.65, p < 0.001$), supporting Hypothesis H1. Simultaneously, in Model 3, after adding the mediating variable academic confidence, testing the direct effect of interpersonal interaction on academic interest revealed that this effect remained significant ($\beta = 0.44, p < 0.001$), and the positive predictive effect of academic confidence on academic interest was also significant ($\beta = 0.47, p < 0.001$), supporting Hypothesis H3.

Table 5 Analysis of the Mediating Role of Academic Confidence between Interpersonal Interaction and Academic Interest

Variable	Model 1:		Model 2:		Model 3:	
	Academic Interest		Academic Confidence		Academic Interest	
	β	t	β	t	β	t
Interpersonal Interaction	0.75	21.00***	0.65	15.76***	0.44	11.18***
Academic Confidence					0.47	11.90***
R ²	0.63		0.51		0.74	
F	36.01***		21.58***		56.52***	

Note: *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$ (two-tailed test)

Figure 2 Mediation Effect Model Path Diagram

Further, the bias-corrected Bootstrap method was used to test the significance of the mediation effect, with interpersonal interaction as the independent variable, academic interest as the dependent variable, and academic confidence as the mediating variable. The sampling size was 5000, with a confidence level of 95%. If the confidence interval does not contain 0, the mediation effect is significant.

The results, as shown in Table 6, indicate that first, the total effect of interpersonal interaction on academic interest was 0.74, with a confidence interval of [0.67, 0.81], not containing 0, indicating that the total effect of interpersonal interaction on academic interest was significant. Second, after controlling for the mediating variable academic confidence, the direct effect of interpersonal interaction on academic interest was 0.44, with a confidence interval of [0.36, 0.52], not containing 0, indicating that the positive direct influence of interpersonal interaction on academic interest was significant. Finally, the mediation effect value of academic confidence between interpersonal interaction and academic interest was 0.31, with a confidence interval of [0.23, 0.39], not containing 0, indicating that academic confidence played a positive and significant partial mediating role between interpersonal interaction and academic interest, supporting Hypothesis H4. In summary, interpersonal interaction positively influences the academic interest of undergraduate top students through academic confidence, with academic confidence playing a partial mediating role.

Table 6 Effect Proportions in the Academic Confidence Mediation Model

	Path	Effect Value	SE	Bootstrap95%CI		Proportion of Total Effect
				Lower Limit	Upper Limit	
Direct Effect	Interpersonal Interaction → Academic Interest	0.44	0.04	0.36	0.52	59.46%
Direct Effect	Interpersonal Interaction → Academic Confidence → Academic Interest	0.31	0.04	0.23	0.39	41.89%
Total Effect	Interpersonal Interaction → Academic Interest	0.74	0.04	0.67	0.81	

Note: *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$ (two-tailed test)

7. Discussion and Recommendations

7.1 Conclusions and Discussion

7.1.1 *Interpersonal interaction can positively influence the academic interest of undergraduate top students.*

The research results indicate that interpersonal interaction significantly positively influences the academic interest of undergraduate top students, further validating the findings of scholars such as Lu Yi and Shi Jinghuan (2015). The results show that different types of interpersonal interaction have varying impacts on the dimensions of academic interest. Specifically: student-student academic interaction can significantly enhance students' level of academic effort; both student-student non-academic interaction and student-teacher academic interaction significantly affect the overall academic interest and its various dimensions; student-teacher social interaction has positive effects on academic loyalty, academic identification, and academic effort. This conclusion is consistent with existing research findings. Shen Yuting (2019) pointed out that teachers and peer groups, as key figures in students' public environment, influence student growth in various aspects such as academic performance and thinking patterns through interaction. Moreover, mentors play a key guiding role in students' academic direction and interest. Wang Peijing et al.'s (2022) research also indicates that "mentors' academic guidance and emotional care are conducive to the cultivation of undergraduates' academic interest". Exploring the underlying reasons, Hidi and Renninger's (2006) "Four-Phase Model of Interest Development" provides a powerful explanation. This theory points out that the evolution of interest needs to go through a qualitative leap process from situational triggering, situational maintenance, to individual emergence, and finally to mature perfection. In this dynamic development, if continuous external emotional support and encouragement are lacking, newly sprouted academic interest can easily stagnate or decline. Peers and teachers, as "companions" and "inspirers" for undergraduate top students, continuously provide crucial academic support and emotional encouragement at different stages of interest development, thereby effectively promoting their academic interest.

7.1.2 *Academic confidence can positively influence the academic interest of undergraduate top students.*

The research results show that academic confidence has a significant positive influence on the academic interest of undergraduate top students, which is consistent with the findings of Adedplim (2013) and Guo Hui et al. (2018). Analyzing from the perspective of self-efficacy theory reveals that an individual's belief in their own ability directly influences their task selection, level of effort, and persistence. Academic confidence, as the core embodiment of self-efficacy in the academic domain, can prompt undergraduate top students to have a higher sense of self-identification, more actively welcome academic challenges, and maintain positive academic emotions when encountering difficulties, continuously nourishing their academic enthusiasm and professional commitment, ultimately making them most likely to pursue further studies or engage in academic careers.

7.1.3 *Academic confidence plays a mediating role in the influence of interpersonal interaction on the academic interest of undergraduate top students.*

The research further finds that academic confidence plays a partial mediating role between interpersonal interaction and academic interest. This means that interpersonal interaction not only directly affects the academic interest of undergraduate top students but also influences it through academic confidence. This conclusion resonates with the views of Wang Peijing (2022) and Yang Yang (2024), and this study extends it to student-student interaction scenarios. The reason for this phenomenon lies in the fact that interpersonal interaction is essentially a key channel for students to enhance their academic confidence. According to Bandura's social cognitive theory, interpersonal interaction enhances academic confidence by providing direct experiences, vicarious experiences, etc., thereby strengthening academic interest. From the perspective of interaction theory, the positive feedback and role identification conveyed in interaction continuously shape students' ability beliefs, promoting the development of academic interest. Therefore, the revelation of this mediating mechanism not only deepens the understanding of the

formation process of academic interest but also provides a theoretical basis and practical path for cultivating students' academic confidence and academic interest by optimizing interpersonal interaction in educational practice.

7.2 Recommendations

7.2.1 Optimize interpersonal interaction to build a diversified support system.

To meet the needs of cultivating academic interest among undergraduate top students, universities should construct a multi-level, high-quality interpersonal interaction system, focusing on synergistic efforts from three dimensions: student-student interaction, student-teacher interaction, and environmental support. At the student-student interaction level, efforts should be made to build cooperative academic communities. Relying on platforms such as top student cultivation base classes and laboratories, students should be encouraged to engage in peer mentoring, collaborative paper writing, and interdisciplinary discussions to form a benign and mutually reinforcing academic atmosphere. Simultaneously, non-academic interaction should continue to be encouraged to promote emotional bonds. At the student-teacher interaction level, the “research mentor system” should be comprehensively deepened, establishing regular communication mechanisms such as academic salons and research group seminars, encouraging mentors to not only focus on academic guidance but also pay attention to emotional support and interest stimulation. Regarding environmental support, universities should strive to create an open and inclusive academic atmosphere, optimize interaction scenarios, and create convenient conditions for cooperative discussions among students and in-depth communication between students and teachers. By organizing activities such as academic forums and summer research projects, the academic horizons and interpersonal networks of top students can be expanded.

7.2.2 Enhance academic confidence to solidify the psychological foundation of academic interest.

Academic confidence is an important bridge linking interpersonal interaction and academic interest. Therefore, an academic psychological support mechanism targeting undergraduate top students should be constructed, consciously strengthening students' ability beliefs and success experiences. University administration should promote the reform of the evaluation system, establishing formative and developmental assessment mechanisms, de-emphasizing single ranking orientation, and strengthening recognition of learning processes, ability progress, and innovative performance to provide students with positive ability feedback. Teachers should scientifically set challenging tasks of appropriate difficulty, accompanied by clear goals, timely feedback, and necessary resources, guiding students to gradually accumulate successful experiences and establish stable ability beliefs. Undergraduate top students should view academic setbacks correctly, enhance psychological resilience, and engage in positive self-attribution, learning to attribute temporary difficulties to the level of effort or strategic methods, rather than insufficient ability. The accumulation of continuous attempts and phased achievements can transform external recognition into stable internal ability beliefs, thereby solidifying the psychological foundation for the development of academic interest.

7.2.3 Pay attention to individual differences and implement classified cultivation.

Individual differences among undergraduate top students should be highly valued during the cultivation process. For top students with clear academic interests, more opportunities for in-depth participation in research and specialized learning can be provided. For students whose interests are still being explored, experiences such as rotating through laboratories and participating in projects across different disciplines can help them gradually find their areas of interest. Schools should respect students' diverse growth paths, not one-sidedly emphasize academic research, but also support students in choosing different development directions such as interdisciplinary studies, innovation, and entrepreneurship. The key is to build suitable academic support platforms tailored to each student's characteristics, helping them find their true academic passion during exploration, and ultimately achieving the rooting and growth of academic interest.

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